

Trajectories of balls on the inclined plane with
numerical examples

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2015

Chapter 1

The frictionless case

Throws are known phenomena. We can call upon throws at sporting events for example. The aim is to get a maximum distance. Another example, is the trajectory of projection of a canonball fired from a canon.

We know trajectories of projection as a part of mechanics. Trajectories are determined by throwing angle and initial velocity. This is valid in vacuum and in a medium e.g. air. We can view trajectories of projection on the inclined plane as well. We will see that the inclined throw in the homogeneous field is a special case of the throw on the inclined plane. Here the trajectories of projection are dependent upon throwing angle and initial velocity, too.

First, we will treat the frictionless case. Thereafter, it will be easier to understand the friction case (chapter 2). In the frictionless case, a ball **slides** on the inclined plane.

a = angle of inclination of the inclined plane
 β = throw angle on the inclined plane $-90^\circ \leq \beta \leq 90^\circ$
 s = distance
 v = velocity
 v_0 = initial velocity
 t = time

On the inclined plane, there is the falling acceleration $g \cdot \sin a$.

Formulation:

$$s_y = \sin \beta \cdot v_0 t - \frac{1}{2} \cdot g \sin a \cdot t^2 \tag{1.1}$$

$$v_y = \frac{ds_y}{dt} = \sin \beta \cdot v_0 - g \sin a \cdot t \tag{1.2}$$

$$s_x = \cos \beta \cdot v_0 t \tag{1.3}$$

Equating (2) to zero and solved to t , then we get the time of ascent t_s for $\beta > 0$:

$$0 = v_y = \sin \beta \cdot v_0 - g \sin a \cdot t_s$$

it follows:

$$t_s = \frac{v_0}{g} \cdot \frac{\sin \beta}{\sin a}$$

t_s inserted in (1) then we yield the maximum altitude of the throw for $\beta > 0$:

$$h_{max} = s_y(t_s) = \frac{\sin \beta \cdot v_0^2 \sin \beta}{g \sin a} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{g \sin a \cdot v_0^2 \sin^2 \beta}{g^2 \cdot \sin^2 a} = \frac{v_0^2 \sin^2 \beta}{g \sin a} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{v_0^2 \sin^2 \beta}{g \sin a}$$

thus

$$h_{max} = \frac{v_0^2 \sin^2 \beta}{2g \sin a}$$

Equating of (1) to zero and solved to t , then we obtain the throwing time t_w for $\beta > 0$:

$$0 = s_y = \sin \beta \cdot v_0 t_w - \frac{1}{2} \cdot g \sin a \cdot t_w^2$$

Transformation:

$$t_w = 2 \cdot \frac{v_0}{g} \cdot \frac{\sin \beta}{\sin a}$$

That means $t_w = 2 \cdot t_s$.

t_w inserted in equation (3), then we get the throwing range w for $\beta > 0$:

$$w = s_x(t_w) = \cos \beta \cdot v_0 t_w = \frac{\cos \beta \cdot v_0 \cdot 2v_0 \sin \beta}{g \sin a} = 2 \cdot \frac{v_0^2}{g} \cdot \frac{\sin \beta \cos \beta}{\sin a}$$

at last we yield:

$$w = \frac{v_0^2}{g} \cdot \frac{\sin(2\beta)}{\sin a}$$

because of $\sin(2\beta) = 2 \sin \beta \cos \beta$

equation (3) solved to t :

$$t = \frac{s_x}{\cos \beta \cdot v_0}$$

and inserted in (1), then we have the equation of the trajectory:

$$s_y = \frac{\sin \beta \cdot v_0 s_x}{v_0 \cos \beta} - \frac{g \sin a \cdot s_x^2}{2 \cos^2 \beta \cdot v_0^2}$$

with $\frac{\sin \beta}{\cos \beta} = \tan \beta$

$$s_y = s_x \cdot \tan \beta - \frac{1}{2} \cdot s_x^2 \cdot \frac{g}{v_0^2} \cdot \frac{\sin a}{\cos^2 \beta}$$

therefore, a parabola

Chapter 2

The case of friction

Now we take into consideration the friction. This consideration is only valid for small relative velocities.

s = distance

v = velocity

b = acceleration

v_0 = initial velocity

a = angle of inclination of the inclined plane

β = throwing angle of the inclined plane $-90^\circ \leq \beta \leq 90^\circ$

$\mu = \frac{\mu'}{R}$ is the rolling friction with rolling friction coefficient μ' and the ball's radius R . (see Assmann [1] chapter 11.10 p.265)

μ_H = static friction coefficient

$$\delta := \begin{cases} \frac{5}{7} & \text{if } \mu' > 0 \text{ (rolling)} \\ 1 & \text{if } \mu' = 0 \text{ (frictionless)} \end{cases}$$

for the ball see Budo [2] §57 p.302 equations (6) - (8)

t = time

In general: $z = s_y \cdot \sin a$ is valid.

The acceleration b on the inclined plane is:

$b = \delta g \cdot \sin a$, the velocity v and the distance s are $v = \delta g \sin a \cdot t$ and $s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta g \cdot t^2 \cdot \sin a$.

If a ball is rolling on the inclined plane, it is $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$ e.g. Budo [2] §57 p.302 equation (8). The moment of inertia J of a ball is $J = \frac{2}{5} \cdot mR^2$. The general formula for rolling on the inclined plane can be written:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin a}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}} \quad (2.1)$$

One derivation can be found at *(p.8), or we can see this with Budo [2] §57 p.302 equations (5)-(7). The ball's moment of inertia insertion leads to:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin a}{m + \frac{2}{5} \cdot m} = \frac{5}{7} \cdot g \sin a \quad (2.2)$$

Then we have in the case of rolling $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$.

For the forces we obtain (see fig.):

$$F = mg \sin a \quad F_N = mg \cos a$$

friction force:

$$F_R = \mu \cdot F_N = mg \mu \cos a$$

In the case of friction:

$$F = mg \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a) \quad b = g \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a) \quad (2.3)$$

$$v = gt \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a) \quad s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot gt^2 (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a)$$

Formulation:

$$v_y = \sin \beta \cdot (v_0 - \mu \cos a \cdot gt) - g \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a) \cdot t \quad (2.4)$$

$$s_y(t) = \int_0^t v_y(\tau) d\tau = \sin \beta \cdot (v_0 t - \mu \cos a \cdot g \cdot \frac{t^2}{2}) - \frac{g}{2} \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a) \cdot t^2 \quad (2.5)$$

$$b_y(t) = \frac{d}{dt} v_y(t) = -\mu \cos a \cdot g \sin \beta - g \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a)$$

For the horizontal component we yield:

$$v_x = \cos \beta \cdot (v_0 - \mu \cos a \cdot gt)$$

$$s_x(t) = \int_0^t v_x(\tau) d\tau$$

it follows:

$$s_x = \cos \beta \cdot (v_0 t - \frac{\mu}{2} \cdot \cos a \cdot gt^2) \quad (2.6)$$

Equating (4) to zero and solved for t , then we get the time of ascent t_s for $\beta > 0$.

$$0 = v_y = \sin \beta \cdot v_0 - \sin \beta \cdot \mu \cos a \cdot gt_s - g\delta \sin a \cdot t_s + g\mu \cos a \cdot t_s$$

Transformation:

$$t_s = \frac{\sin \beta \cdot v_0}{\sin \beta \cdot \mu \cos a \cdot g + g \delta \sin a - g \mu \cos a}$$

at last:

$$t_s = \frac{\sin \beta \cdot v_0}{\mu \cos a \cdot g \cdot (\sin \beta - 1) + g \delta \sin a}$$

If we insert t_s in t in (5), we obtain the maximum altitude $h_{max} := s_y(t_s)$.

Equating (5) to zero and solved for t , then we get the throwing time t_w for $\beta > 0$.

$$0 = s_y = \sin \beta \cdot v_0 t_w - \mu \cos a \cdot g \cdot \frac{t_w^2}{2} \cdot \sin \beta - \frac{g}{2} \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a) \cdot t_w^2$$

Solving:

$$t_w = \frac{2 \cdot \sin \beta \cdot v_0}{\mu \cos a \cdot g \sin \beta + g \cdot (\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a)}$$

Inserted t_w in t in (6), then we get the throwing range $w = s_x(t_w)$ for $\beta > 0$. Then it is $s_y(t_w) = 0$.

In the case $\delta \sin a - \mu \cos a \leq 0$ there is no free falling.

$$\Leftrightarrow \delta \sin a \leq \mu \cos a$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \tan a \leq \frac{\mu}{\delta} \quad \text{because of} \quad \tan a = \frac{\sin a}{\cos a}$$

In this case we have:

$$v_y = \sin \beta \cdot (v_0 - \mu \cos a \cdot gt) \quad (2.7)$$

$$s_y(t) = \int_0^t v_y(\tau) d\tau = \sin \beta \cdot \left(v_0 t - \mu \cos a \cdot g \cdot \frac{t^2}{2} \right) \quad (2.8)$$

Equating (7) to zero and solved for t , then we yield the time t_E . After this time, the ball stands still.

$$0 = \sin \beta \cdot (v_0 - \mu \cos a \cdot gt_E)$$

transformed:

$$t_E = \frac{v_0}{\mu \cos a \cdot g}$$

Inserted t_E in t in (8), then we get the altitude at the end h_E :

$$h_E = s_y(t_E) = \sin \beta \cdot \left(v_0 \cdot \frac{v_0}{\mu \cos a \cdot g} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \mu \cos a \cdot g \cdot \frac{v_0^2}{\mu^2 \cos^2 a \cdot g^2} \right)$$

$$= \frac{\sin \beta \cdot v_0^2}{\mu \cos a \cdot g} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{v_0^2 \sin \beta}{\mu \cos a \cdot g}$$

We obtain:

$$h_E = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{\sin \beta \cdot v_0^2}{\mu \cos a \cdot g}$$

In the case $\beta \leq 0$ there is no t_s and t_w .

More difficult is the treatment in consideration of a medium (gas, liquid).

Some remarks to the validity of these equations:

The sliding friction must be locked out, as in Budo [2] §57 p.302 equation (10) at the ball, it is valid $\tan a \leq \frac{7}{2} \cdot \mu_H$. That means only at a small angle of inclination is the sliding friction locked out. The relative velocity must be small. Lastly, the ball and the inclined plane must be elastic. This is true for steel balls and the steel underlayer.

to *: The derivation of formula (1):

Notations:

$$\text{kinetic energy} = E_{kin} = \frac{mv^2}{2}$$

$$\text{potential energy} = E_{pot} = mgh \text{ with } h = h_s \sin a \text{ vgl. fig.}$$

$$\text{rotational energy} = E_{rot} = \frac{Jw^2}{2} \quad J = \text{moment of inertia}$$

law of conservation of energy:

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jw^2}{2} = mgh$$

We assume that the body is only rolling not sliding. Then it is valid:

$$\text{angular velocity} = w = \frac{v}{R} \quad R = \text{radius of the rolling body}$$

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jv^2}{2R^2} = mgh_s \sin a$$

With transformation we yield:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2mgh_s \sin a}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}}$$

Because the rolling body has the constant acceleration $b = g \sin a$, there is a uniform acceleration motion. For this motion it is valid: $v^2 = 2h_s \cdot b$ transformed to $b = \frac{v^2}{2h_s}$. Now we insert the equation of v :

$$b = \frac{2mgh_s \sin a}{2h_s \cdot (m + \frac{J}{R^2})} = \frac{mg \sin a}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}$$

Then we have the wanted formula.

Now we treat numerical examples. We have a steel underlayer and a steel ball. The ball's radius is 2 millimetres. The rolling friction coefficient has got the value 0.002 m^{-1} . The limit friction angle is 54.46° . Over 74.06° the slide friction must be taken into consideration. First we turn to the case $a=30^\circ$. We calculate $t_E=0.2354$ seconds at a initial velocity of 2 metres per second. In this case the time of climb is equal to the throwing time= t_E and the maximum altitude= h_E . We view the following table:

throwing angle in degree	maximum altitude in metres	throwing range in metres
10	0.041	0.232
20	0.081	0.221
30	0.118	0.204
40	0.151	0.180
50	0.180	0.151
60	0.204	0.118
70	0.221	0.081
80	0.232	0.041
89	0.235	0.004

Now we choose the throwing angle= 20 degree and we view this throw with the following table. The unit of the velocity components is metres per second. s_x and s_y are calculated in metres:

$t[\text{sec}]$	v_x	s_x	v_y	s_y	$v(\text{absolute value})$
0	1.879	0	0.684	0	2
0.02	1.720	0.036	0.678	0.013	1.849
0.04	1.560	0.069	0.568	0.025	1.660
0.06	1.400	0.098	0.510	0.036	1.490
0.08	1.241	0.125	0.452	0.045	1.320
0.10	1.081	0.148	0.393	0.054	1.150
0.12	0.921	0.168	0.335	0.061	0.981
0.14	0.752	0.185	0.277	0.067	0.801
0.16	0.602	0.199	0.219	0.072	0.641
0.18	0.442	0.209	0.161	0.076	0.471
0.20	0.283	0.216	0.103	0.079	0.301
0.22	0.123	0.220	0.045	0.080	0.131
t_E	0	0.221	0	$0.081 = h_E$	0

Now we change the angle of inclination (of the plane) to 60° . In this case t_E and h_E don't exist. The other quantities remain unchanged. We show the dependence from the throwing angle with the following table, times in seconds, paths in metres:

throwing angle in degree	time of ascent	throwing time	maximum altitude	throwing range
10	0.172	0.344	0.030	0.402
20	0.241	0.482	0.082	0.383
30	0.277	0.554	0.138	0.353
40	0.298	0.596	0.191	0.312
50	0.311	0.622	0.239	0.262
60	0.320	0.640	0.277	0.204
70	0.326	0.652	0.306	0.139
80	0.329	0.658	0.324	0.071
89	0.330	0.660	0.330	0.007

Now we choose the throwing angle 50° and we view the throw as in the second table, time in seconds, velocities in metres per second and paths in metres:

t	v_x	s_x	v_y	s_y	$v(\text{absolute value})$
0	1.286	0	1.532	0	2
0.04	1.159	0.049	1.335	0.057	1.768
0.08	1.033	0.093	1.138	0.107	1.537
0.12	0.907	0.132	0.942	0.148	1.308
0.16	0.781	0.165	0.745	0.182	1.079
0.20	0.655	0.194	0.548	0.208	0.854
0.24	0.529	0.218	0.351	0.226	0.635
0.28	0.403	0.236	0.154	0.236	0.431
0.32	0.277	0.250	-0.043	0.238	0.280
0.36	0.151	0.259	-0.239	0.233	0.283
0.40	0.024	0.262	-0.436	0.219	0.437

Bibliography

- [1] Bruno Assmann "Technische Mechanik" volume 1 Oldenbourg Verlag 12.edition Munich 1991
- [2] A Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften Berlin 1980